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Analysis of the development trend of Artificial Intelligence in Kenya and the Prospects of China-Kenya Cooperation

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Abstract

Kenya's AI development is in a period of rapid growth. The construction of its digital economy and technology ecosystem, the formulation of AI strategies, the application of AI, and the education of AI talents are gradually accelerating and improving. Although Kenya has great potential in the development of AI, it still faces challenges such as technological gaps, insufficient protection of data privacy and incomplete policies and regulations. As an important partner, China has provided significant support for Kenya's AI development through technology transfer, infrastructure construction and talent cultivation. In the future, deepening AI cooperation between China and Kenya will be an important path to promote technological progress and economic development in Kenya. This includes focusing on agriculture as a key area for AI cooperation between China and Kenya, strengthening talent cultivation and capacity building, attaching importance to enhancing digital knowledge and capabilities of Kenyan women, jointly addressing "human rights" risks by the government and enterprises, and promoting AI cooperation between China and the United States to support the development of AI in Kenya. China-kenya cooperation will not only bring innovative impetus to Kenya's AI development, but also provide new opportunities for cooperation between the two countries in the global technological competition.

Keywords: Kenya; Artificial Intelligence; China-Africa Cooperation

1. Introduction

1.1. The current situation of artificial intelligence development in Kenya

1.1.1. *The construction of the digital economy and technological ecosystem is gradually accelerating*

Kenya's digital economy and technology ecosystem refers to the country's comprehensive framework for promoting economic growth and innovation through digital technologies. It covers Internet infrastructure, e-commerce platforms, fintech (such as M-Pesa), start-up companies, technology incubators, government policy support, and the application of various digital services in fields such as agriculture, education, and healthcare. The core objective of this ecosystem is to promote inclusive growth, enhance productivity and facilitate social development.

Kenya's digital economy has demonstrated strong vitality, especially in the fields of mobile payment and e-commerce. As early as 2004, Kenya launched its e-government strategy and released its first national information and communication technology (ICT) policy in 2005. In 2008, the government emphasized the strengthening of the application of scientific and technological innovation through the "Vision 2030" policy, in order to enhance the productivity and efficiency of the three major economic pillars and promote the rapid development of the technological

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ecosystem. The "Kenya National ICT Master Plan 2014-2017" released in 2014 further utilized the huge potential of ICT to promote social and economic growth. Enable Kenya to move towards a knowledge economy and a regional information technology center. Driven by these policies, Kenya's digital economy and technology ecosystem has developed rapidly, as follows:

- Internet penetration rate: As of early 2024, Kenya's Internet penetration rate has reached 40.8%, with over 22.71 million Internet users and 13.05 million social media users, accounting for 23.5% of the total population.
- Mobile user penetration rate: Kenya has a total of 66.04 million active cellular mobile connections, with a penetration rate of 118.7%.**Error! Reference source not found.**
- 5G Network Development: As one of the earliest countries in Africa to launch 5G networks, by the end of 2023, Kenya had over 500,000 5G network users. According to gsma intelligence's prediction, the number of 5G network connections in Kenya will reach 2.8 million in 2025 and exceed 19.8 million in 2030.
- Mobile Payment: The penetration rate of mobile payment in Kenya is extremely high. It has one of the world's largest mobile payment platforms, M-Pesa. M-Pesa has over 50 million customers in 7 countries and serves more than 5 million enterprises. 59% of Kenya's annual GDP flows through it.**Error! Reference source not found.**
- E-commerce: In 2021, Kenya's e-commerce revenue reached 1.268 billion US dollars and is expected to grow to 1.964 billion US dollars by 2025.**Error! Reference source not found.**
- Startups and Technology Incubators: Kenya's startup ecosystem is highly dynamic, featuring several well-known technology incubators such as iHub, NaiLab, NakuruBox, and the Kenya Climate Innovation Center (KCIC), which provide startups with funding, guidance, and office space.
- Digital Service Applications: Digital technologies are widely applied in fields such as agriculture, education and healthcare. For instance, mobile applications provide agricultural information to farmers, while electronic education platforms offer distance education services to students.

1.2. Accelerate the formulation of an artificial intelligence strategy

In recent years, to promote the economic and social development of Kenya, the Kenyan government has attached great importance to the development of the AI industry and gradually increased its investment in the AI field. As early as 2018, the government established a Distributed ledger Technology (DLT) and AI working group to explore the application prospects of AI technology in the country. In 2019, the report released by this working group pointed out that AI and other cutting-edge technologies could enhance Kenya's national competitiveness and accelerate the innovation process. Against this backdrop, AI technology has gradually permeated various industries in Kenya. In 2022, Kenya released The "The Kenya National Digital Master Plan 2022-2032", which explicitly stated its support for formulating the national AI strategy and listed AI as an important field of emerging technologies.**Error! Reference source not found.**With the advent of ChatGPT in 2023, AI has drawn global attention, and the long-term lack of policy support and strategic guidance in Kenya's AI industry has also drawn the government's attention. In December 2023, Kenya passed The "Kenya robotics and artificial intelligence society bill 2023" (hereinafter referred to as the "AI Bill"). In April 2024, the Kenyan government officially launched the formulation of a national AI strategy named "Fair Forward - Artificial Intelligence for All".**Error! Reference source not found.**

1.3. The application fields of artificial intelligence are gradually expanding

AI has been widely applied in enterprises and people's lives in Kenya. According to a 2022 study by the Kenya Intellectual Property and Information Technology Law Research Center (CIPIT), the 49 application scenarios of AI in Kenya cover at least 15 industries, among which agriculture, health, finance, education and security are the most important application fields.**Error! Reference source not found.**In the agricultural sector, AI technology is employed to enhance farmers' productivity and predict climate change and market trends through data analysis to promote sustainable development. In the field of health, AI is used for disease prediction and remote diagnosis, helping to improve medical services in remote areas. In the financial sector, AI-driven fintech has promoted financial inclusiveness and provided personalized services to users. In the field of education, AI analyzes students' learning situations and tailors personalized teaching resources for them. In the field of security, AI helps manage social media, monitor and combat online hate speech, and safeguard national security. Furthermore, a 2024 Stanford AI Index study indicates that 27% of Kenyans use ChatGPT every day, ranking third globally, only after India and Pakistan. Kenya also has 106 AI startups, 42 top AI companies and 2,500 AI professionals, demonstrating its huge potential in the AI field.**Error! Reference source not found.**

1.4. The educational level of artificial intelligence talents has been gradually improving

The Kenyan government attaches great importance to the cultivation of AI talents. In 2022, Kenya became the first country in Africa to introduce programming courses in primary and secondary schools, promoting early education for the next generation of AI technology talents. In 2023, Jomo Kenyatta University took the lead among Kenyan universities in holding a series of AI academic activities such as the "National AI and Machine Learning Symposium", aiming to consolidate Kenya's position as a center of AI talents in Africa. At present, Kenya's AI higher education system covers skills training, undergraduate education and postgraduate education. At least three universities have established a complete AI discipline system, covering undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral education. In addition to government investment, enterprises are also actively responding to the demand for AI talents. In 2023, Amazon Web Services (AWS) collaborated with the Kenyan government to launch the "AI Ready" program, with the goal of providing free AI skills training to at least two million Kenyans by 2025. **Error! Reference source not found.** In addition, Dedan Kimathi University of Technology, as well as several technology enterprises and organizations, have also actively participated in the cultivation and training of AI talents, promoting the all-round development of AI talent education.

2. The future development path of artificial intelligence in Kenya

Although Kenya has demonstrated great potential in the field of artificial intelligence (AI), its development still faces some challenges. Problems such as insufficient broadband coverage, lack of data centers and shortage of technical talents still hinder the wide application of AI. At the same time, the ethical issues brought about by AI technology and the demand for data privacy protection also urgently need policy guidance. To address these challenges, the Kenyan government and enterprises regard international cooperation as a key strategy, taking strengthening infrastructure construction as the foundation for AI development, enhancing AI regulation and governance as the security guarantee, and strengthening talent cultivation to ensure the innovation and sustainable development of AI.

2.1. International cooperation

Kenya attaches great importance to international cooperation in the field of AI. The AI Act proposes to encourage partnerships with international organizations, research institutions and industry leaders to promote knowledge sharing and ensure that Kenya remains at the forefront of global technological development. Kenya's National Digital Development Plan (2022-2032) also clearly states that in the future, it will strengthen cooperation with other countries in the research and development of emerging technologies such as AI. **Error! Reference source not found.** In recent years, Kenya has carried out extensive cooperation with countries such as the European Union, the United States, and China in areas like digital infrastructure construction, talent cultivation, and technological innovation. For instance, Kenya has jointly formulated its national AI strategy with the German Development Cooperation Agency (GIZ) and received support from the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ). In addition, the United States and Kenya signed a cooperation statement on AI research and standard setting. The two sides plan to enhance cooperation among governments, industries and academic institutions through collaboration. In 2024, Kenya and the United Arab Emirates signed an agreement. Microsoft and the UAE AI company G42 will invest 1 billion US dollars in Kenya to build a data center, further promoting the construction of AI infrastructure.

2.2. Strengthen infrastructure construction

The Kenyan government recognizes that digital infrastructure is the foundation for unlocking the potential of AI, and thus has increased its investment in networks, data centers and cloud computing services. The key points of future planning include: enhancing the construction of Internet infrastructure, especially in remote areas; Develop local data centers to enhance data storage and processing capabilities; Encourage private enterprises to develop cloud computing platforms; Improve the data governance framework to ensure data security and privacy protection; Strengthen cooperation with higher education institutions and training organizations to enhance the cultivation level of local digital technology talents. Meanwhile, the Kenyan government is actively seeking international cooperation, introducing foreign capital and technical support to accelerate the upgrading of digital infrastructure.

2.3. Strengthen the supervision and governance of artificial intelligence

Kenya still faces deficiencies in AI regulation, especially in terms of preventing the abuse of AI technology and maintaining privacy protection, where legislative improvements are urgently needed. The AI Act, which was introduced in 2023, explains the regulatory functions of the Robotics and AI Association. However, experts believe that there is still room for improvement in the role and responsibility division of the act. In the future, Kenya needs to establish a more comprehensive AI regulatory system, covering the responsibilities of the national and local governments in the development of AI, and addressing the ethical, legal and social issues brought about by AI. **Error! Reference source not found.** The "Code of Conduct for AI Applications" to be released in 2024 for the first time clearly defined the responsibilities of AI technology providers and recommended promoting the establishment of a risk management and legal system. In

addition, the government has also taken measures to curb the generation of false information by AI and is paying attention to the social inequality issues brought about by AI.

2.4. Talent cultivation

Kenya has gradually introduced AI education in primary and secondary schools as well as higher education, but it still needs to significantly enhance talent cultivation. According to the "Kenya National Digital Development Plan (2022-2032)", the future development of AI will rely on an adequate number of researchers and technical talents. Error! Reference source not found. The demand for AI courses in Kenya is growing rapidly, especially in the fields of online education and continuing education. For instance, data released by Google in September 2023 indicated that the query volume for virtual assistant courses in Kenya increased by 450%, while the query volumes for data analysis courses and digital marketing courses both rose by 200%. To address this trend, the Kenyan government plans to provide sufficient funds for AI training programs. Moreover, Kenya intends to optimize AI courses, invest in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) education, strengthen public-private partnerships, implement extensive digital literacy programs, establish AI research centers, and enhance the popularity of AI online learning platforms. Promote international cooperation projects and other measures to cultivate a workforce capable of leading the innovative development of AI.

3. Opportunities and Challenges of artificial Intelligence Cooperation between China and Kenya

China's scientific and technological cooperation with Africa initially focused on the infrastructure sector and has gradually expanded to information and communication technology (ICT) and the digital economy in recent years. China's rapid development in fields such as AI, big data, and cloud computing has provided opportunities for technology transfer and cooperation for African countries. Through the Belt and Road Initiative, China-Africa cooperation has promoted in-depth integration in the field of science and technology, especially in the construction of ICT infrastructure and technical training.

3.1. Opportunities for China-Kenya cooperation in artificial intelligence

First of all, China's AI development ranks among the world's top, with the largest number of patent applications globally, and it is compatible with various AI application fields in Kenya. In the agricultural sector, the agricultural digital platform of Luoyang iFLYTEK Company has significantly enhanced the efficiency of agricultural planting. In the medical field, the AI pathological diagnosis products of Ice Technology have significantly enhanced the efficiency of doctors in processing pathological data. In the financial sector, the "Kungfu Quantification" AI application of Kungfu Source Technology helps ordinary investors analyze market data. In the field of education, the 18 "AI+ Education" applications announced by the Ministry of Education have covered the teaching process of colleges and universities. In the field of safety, Safe City has established a city safety management network for over 100 cities in more than 30 countries around the world.

Secondly, China has played a significant role in Kenya's digital infrastructure construction, helping the country establish key infrastructure such as fiber-optic networks and data centers, enhancing its digital capabilities and ensuring the implementation of AI technologies. In addition, the cooperation between the two sides in fields such as cloud computing, big data and the Internet of Things has also laid a technical foundation for future AI applications. For instance, between 2000 and 2017, Kenya received three AI application projects from China, among which the Safe City system built by Huawei in Nairobi, Kenya in 2015 was the most eye-catching. Huawei has built a safe city system in Nairobi, Kenya. By connecting and setting up 1,800 high-definition cameras and 200 traffic monitoring systems, as well as helping to establish a national police command center, it supports the monitoring and case-solving work of over 9,000 police officers in 195 police stations. Error! Reference source not found.

In addition, Chinese enterprises such as Huawei and Alibaba have promoted cooperation with Kenya in the fields of digital economy and AI through the Belt and Road Initiative, helping local enterprises and government agencies enhance their technological capabilities. For instance, Huawei has collaborated with Kenyan mobile operator Safaricom to build three 5G experience centers. Nanjing Laisi Information Technology Co., Ltd. has also provided urban traffic management tools and AI music applications for Kenya. China also actively supports Kenya's AI development through talent cultivation programs. Huawei ICT Academy provides training for Kenyan students and technicians, enhancing the AI development and application capabilities of local technicians.

In conclusion, China's technology transfer and investment have accelerated Kenya's infrastructure construction and technological capacity improvement, enabling it to integrate into global technological competition and cooperation more quickly. China's experience in AI application has provided innovative solutions for key sectors such as agriculture, healthcare and finance in Kenya.

3.2. The challenges of China-Kenya cooperation in artificial intelligence

China-kenya AI cooperation is confronted with common challenges such as differences in technical foundations, economic imbalances, financing difficulties, as well as social acceptance and employment issues. In addition, it is necessary to pay attention to the deviation of data collection and processing models, the fairness of algorithms, governance responsibilities, and the impact of external competition.

First of all, AI collaboration may involve "human rights" risks. First of all, the cooperation between China and Kenya on AI may involve "human rights" risks. The application of AI technology in data collection and monitoring may infringe upon personal privacy. If there is no effective legal and regulatory framework, the abuse of AI may raise human rights issues and trigger widespread questioning and protests against human rights. Kenyan citizens are concerned about the government's use of technologies such as AI facial recognition tools to monitor citizens' activities, believing that this not only fails to effectively reduce crime but may also become a tool to suppress dissent. Moreover, the insufficient transparency in the use of these AI technologies and the lack of public participation have exacerbated this problem. The Kenyan government's awareness of the impact of its use also needs to be enhanced. Kenyan people believe that the government's weaponization of AI may undermine freedom of speech and freedom of association.^{Error! Reference source not found.}Therefore, when conducting AI cooperation between China and Kenya, special attention should be paid to sensitive AI fields such as data security and privacy protection.

Secondly, there are risks of gender and educational inequality in AI collaboration. If the development and application of AI lack gender sensitivity, it may exacerbate social inequality. The gender ratio in the AI field in Africa is 71% to 29%. Women account for 13% of chief executive officers and only 10% of founders of AI companies.^{Error! Reference source not found.}In Kenya, 58% of men use mobile Internet, while the figure for women is 39%. This may lead to insufficient data on effective female users to train AI algorithms. Moreover, there are relatively few female practitioners in the AI field in Kenya. These issues make it difficult for the design and application of AI systems to fully take into account the needs of women. Meanwhile, the imbalance of educational resources makes it difficult for students in remote areas to receive training in AI-related skills, which hinders their participation in the future development of AI.^{Error! Reference source not found.}

Finally, competition among major powers outside the region has exacerbated the complexity of AI cooperation between China and Kenya. In recent years, the United States has been competing with China in the field of technology on the African continent, and AI has become one of the focuses. Under the guidance of the "Africa Digital Transformation" strategy, the United States is promoting partnerships with African countries and strengthening its influence in the field of science and technology through corporate investment, technology exports, and the export of AI-related regulations and standards. Kenya, as a bridgehead for the United States to promote AI in Africa, signed multiple AI agreements with the US government in 2024. At present, many large American technology companies have established AI research laboratories in Kenya. Microsoft established Microsoft Research Africa in Nairobi, Kenya in 2020. IBM Research also established a laboratory in Nairobi in 2016 and announced the establishment of a product development center in 2022. Meanwhile, the United States is attempting to join forces with the United Arab Emirates to jointly counter China's superiority in AI technology development.^{Error! Reference source not found.}

4. Suggestions for China and Kenya to carry out artificial intelligence cooperation

4.1. Take agriculture as the key area of cooperation between China and Kenya in AI

Agriculture accounts for approximately 25% of Kenya's gross domestic product (GDP), and over 70% of the workforce is engaged in agriculture. As a developing country, agriculture is crucial to Kenya's food security, employment and economic growth. However, Kenya's agriculture is currently confronted with challenges such as climate change, low productivity and resource shortages, and traditional agricultural methods are no longer capable of coping. To this end, the government hopes to enhance production efficiency through precision agriculture technology and optimize the supply chain through big data analysis to strengthen food security.^{Error! Reference source not found.}As a major agricultural country, China possesses advanced intelligent agricultural technologies, agricultural data platforms and risk management experience, which can provide support for the modernization of agriculture in Kenya. Moreover, the

agricultural sector, as a livelihood project in China-Kenya cooperation, can bring multiple positive impacts to China, including enhancing its reputation and image in Kenyan society, market expansion and economic benefits, and establishing a demonstration effect in Africa. Therefore, Zhongken can take agriculture as a key area for AI cooperation. AI collaboration in the agricultural sector can not only help Kenya enhance food security but also drive the modernization of its rural areas. China should promote the signing of agricultural AI cooperation agreements and cooperate with local non-governmental organizations to popularize agricultural AI technologies and experiences in Kenya.

4.2. Strengthen talent cultivation and capacity building

Traditional international cooperation has mainly focused on the transfer of funds and technologies. With the increasing demand for sustainable solutions in developing countries and the changing international public opinion environment, capacity building has become the key to cooperation. Against this backdrop, China should continue to deepen cooperation with Kenya in the field of AI, especially in key technology areas such as machine learning and natural language processing. Through technology transfer and cooperative development, efforts should be made to promote the construction of Kenya's local AI research and development capabilities. Meanwhile, both sides should enhance cooperation in talent cultivation. Through university cooperation, enterprise training and technical exchange programs, they should help Kenya train local AI technology experts. China can encourage domestic higher education institutions to cooperate with Kenyan universities and provide special financial support for Kenyan students to study in China, enhancing their capabilities in AI technology and application. Specifically, China can encourage domestic higher education institutions to cooperate with Kenyan universities, especially the University of Nairobi, Jomo Kenyatta University and the Intellectual Property and Information Technology Law Research Center of Strathmore University. The Chinese government can also encourage domestic universities to accept Kenyan students and provide special financial support for them to study AI technology and its applications in China.

4.3. Attach importance to the improvement of digital knowledge and capabilities of Kenyan women

In its cooperation with Kenya, China should pay particular attention to enhancing women's digital knowledge and capabilities. This is an important measure to promote Kenya's economic growth, social inclusion and digital economy development. It will also enhance China's international image and soft power in Africa and promote more sustainable and diverse China-Africa cooperation. The successful experience of the United States in Kenya is worth learning from. This includes the Women Digital Leaders Training Program of the National Telecommunications and Information Administration (NTIA) of the United States, as well as enhancing women's digital skills through education and training, such as the "WomenConnect" of the United States Agency for International Development (USAID The "Challenge" project, promoting women's participation in technology entrepreneurship such as Microsoft's "4Afrika" initiative, advancing gender equality and inclusive policies in the technology field such as the gender inclusion project funded by the United States Agency for International Development in Kenya, and improving women's digital capabilities in agriculture such as the "FarmDrive" project jointly launched by the United States Agency for International Development and IBM And other practices such as using digital technology to solve social problems faced by women. Drawing on these practices, China can enhance the participation and capabilities of Kenyan women in the field of science and technology by funding visits to China by Kenyan female elites or organizing women's science and technology dialogues, demonstrating its emphasis on the development of women in science and technology.

4.4. The government and enterprises work together to address "human rights" risks

In Sino-Kenyan AI cooperation, attention should be paid to human rights issues such as data privacy and algorithmic bias that may be brought about by AI technology. This not only involves the legality and ethics of the cooperation, but also relates to international reputation and the sustainability of long-term cooperation. For instance, in 2024, 97 Kenyan tech workers jointly wrote to US President Joe Biden, claiming that the AI work conditions they were engaged in at companies like OpenAI were equivalent to "modern slavery". This is because they train AI models at a wage of less than 2 dollars per hour, while their job tasks require them to recognize and read a large amount of harmful information, which has caused great harm to their physical and mental health.^{Error! Reference source not found.} This move by American enterprises has seriously undermined Kenya's labor laws and violated international labor standards, and also serves as a wake-up call for Chinese AI enterprises in Kenya.

Therefore, the Chinese government and enterprises should enhance communication to ensure that Chinese enterprises comply with labor laws and AI-related regulations in Kenya, avoiding "malicious incidents" such as the exploitation of Kenyan workers and encountering "human rights issues". At the same time, promote cultural understanding and gender balance among local employees to facilitate mutual benefit and win-win results between China and Kenya. For instance, when recruiting Kenyan employees, it is necessary to maintain a moderate ratio of men to women as much as possible

and provide opportunities for people in remote areas, such as setting up funds or scholarships, to promote China-Kenya friendship based on AI cooperation. The government should also promote the integration of resources, overall coordination, group expansion and healthy competition among Chinese AI enterprises going global, and avoid internal vicious competition such as "price wars". In addition, the Chinese government and enterprises should actively participate in the formulation of Kenya's AI policies and regulatory framework, helping Kenya establish an AI governance system that suits its national conditions. This can not only avoid human rights risks but also enhance China's influence in global AI governance.

4.5. Promoting AI cooperation between China and the United States to facilitate the development of AI in Kenya

China has an advantage in data resources and application scenarios, while the United States leads in the field of algorithm research and development. China and the United States are complementary in the field of AI, and importantly, many American enterprises are willing to establish partnerships with Chinese enterprises. By promoting cooperation between the two countries in the complementary field of AI, not only can technological competition be alleviated, but also technological and resource improvements can be brought to African countries such as Kenya. This cooperation is in line with the spirit of global multilateralism and promotes AI technology to become an important tool for addressing global challenges. Therefore, China and the United States should establish a high-level dialogue mechanism in the field of AI, conduct regular consultations on AI technology, standards and ethical issues, to ensure that conflicts are avoided in sensitive areas. In May 2024, China and the United States held their first inter-governmental meeting on AI. This dialogue is a positive step in the competitive and cooperative relationship between the two countries in the field of AI, providing a platform for the two countries to discuss and understand each other's positions.

Based on the current background of Sino-US relations, the following areas of AI cooperation between China and the US are relatively feasible: First, cooperation among AI research institutions, especially in jointly developing AI technologies on some global issues (such as healthcare, agriculture, and energy). For instance, in Kenya's agricultural sector, China could encourage AI enterprises to collaborate with the US private sector, the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, and higher education institutions, among others. By leveraging AI, they can recommend the best seeds for farmers based on local soil and weather conditions, develop drugs and vaccines for livestock, and better predict crop yields. This will increase profits and create a more reliable food supply, etc. Second, build an industrial cooperation platform, including joint product development, exploring the Kenyan and even African markets, and sharing experiences in AI application scenarios and commercialization models, such as promoting the commercialization of 5G and VR games in Kenya. Thirdly, China and the United States can jointly initiate a global AI innovation fund, focusing on supporting the development of AI in developing countries, especially in African countries like Kenya, and promoting the application of AI technology in fields such as agriculture, healthcare, and education. In addition, strengthening standardization and regulatory coordination, as well as jointly participating in AI ethical governance, are key steps for China and the United States to move towards deeper cooperation and make positive contributions to promoting global AI development.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that Kenya is experiencing rapid growth in artificial intelligence, supported by a dynamic digital economy and increasing international partnerships, yet it continues to face significant challenges in infrastructure, regulation, and equitable access. The analysis highlights the substantial role that China-Kenya cooperation can play in addressing these gaps through technology transfer, talent development, and ethical governance. This research will benefit society by offering actionable insights for policymakers and stakeholders to foster inclusive and sustainable AI development in Kenya, with a way forward emphasizing multi-stakeholder collaboration and context-sensitive innovation.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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